

NFDI4Earth

Milestone MS3.1.2

Extended service catalogue

Kemeng Liu ,
Stephan Frickenhaus

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Executive summary

This report presents our progress in establishing a service catalogue within the context of NFDI4Earth. By evaluating upper-level or existing metadata schema for research data management services, we have developed a metadata schema for mapping research data management services into the knowledge graph database (Knowledge Hub) of NFDI4Earth. Additionally, we provide updates on several repositories via re3data, which is considered part of the NFDI4Earth service catalogue.

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1. Introduction

Within NFDI4Earth, managing information on research data management (RDM) services is a key task. In our previous report on the “NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue and Gap Analysis”¹, we outlined initial ideas for shaping the service catalogue and identified gaps between our goal of achieving FAIRness and the existing services that cannot fulfill these requirements. Building on the previous work, we have now developed a metadata schema that describes RDM service instances more comprehensively and enables better interoperability with existing upper-level schemas.

2. Updated Repository Information

NFDI4Earth has deepened its collaboration with re3data (Registry of Research Data Repositories)^{2,3}, which serves as the project’s primary source of repository information. Since we have published our report “NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue and Gap Analysis”, the information on several repositories was updated at re3data. As described in the report, NFDI4Earth collaborates with re3data by forwarding information on missing or incorrect metadata fields and outdated repository entries. When a repository is identified that is not yet registered with re3data, NFDI4Earth consults the repository providers in the registration process with re3data. In this way, re3data and the NFDI4Earth have established a very successful and timely exchange of updated information. In the following table a selection of repositories is highlighted that have been updated in re3data in 2025 (Tab. 1). However, many more NFDI4Earth-related repositories regularly update their records.

Table 1: Overview of selected updated repositories

Infrastructure (repository)	URL	Status
ATTO	https://www.attodata.org/home/Start	Registered at re3data on 2024-07-24
GDI-DE (Geodatenkatalog)	https://gdk.gdi-de.org/gdi-de/srv/eng/catalog.search#/home	Registered at re3data on 2024-05-15
HCDC	https://hcdc.hereon.de/datasearch/	Registered at re3data on 2023-11-21
GEOROC	https://georoc.eu/ and https://data.goettingen-research-online.de/dataverse/digis	Information updated at re3data on 2024-09-13

¹ Müller, C. M., & Frickenhaus, S. (2023). NFDI4Earth Service Catalogue and Gap Analysis (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8344438>

² <https://www.re3data.org/>

³ Frickenhaus, S., Grieb, J., Henzen, C., Müller, C., Protopopova-Kakar, V., & Weiland, C. (2025). NFDI4Earth Cooperation - re3data (NFDI4Earth White Paper). NFDI4Earth Community on Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15095431>

A full list of repositories is available in our NFDI4Earth-developed services OneStop4All⁴ and Knowledge Hub⁵.

3. RDM services

The concept of Research Data Management (RDM) describes a process of handling research data from creation to dissemination and archiving, encompassing the research data lifecycle in a structured way⁶. In the community of Earth System Science (ESS), just as in many other scientific domains, research data management is seen as essential for verifying research results and fostering future research based on existing knowledge⁶. Research data management is generally supported by various RDM services. In the NFDI, RDM services are understood as a “technical-organisational solution including storage and computing services, software, processes, and workflows, as well as the necessary personnel support for different service desks”^{7,8}. There are also other definitions of RDM services available in a broader sense. For example, EOSC encompasses RDM services in the broader category of EOSC resources⁹, which include services that support data management, preservation, access, and reuse. While for example NASA’s Earth Science Data Systems (ESDS)¹⁰ employs a “Level of Service model”, which consistently stewards data across its archives. According to the NASA concept, it depends on the level (basic, standard, comprehensive), and services include data ingestion, preservation, documentation, distribution, usability, user support, outreach, and long-term preservation. There are some examples, where institutions refer to the term “RDM services” as “Support Services”, as for example the University of Freiburg, where such services are collected as a RDM Services Catalogue along the Research Data Life Cycle¹¹.

⁴ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/search?resourcetype=Repository+%26+Archive&sort=>

⁵ <https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de/>

⁶ Whyte, A., Tedds, J. (2011). ‘Making the Case for Research Data Management’. DCC Briefing Papers. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. Available Online: <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/briefing-papers/making-case-rdm>

⁷ ⁷ Henzen, C., Brauer, A., Degbelo, A., Frickenhaus, S., Grieb, J., Hachinger, S., Klammer, R., Müller, C., Munke, J., Niers, T., Nüst, D., Weiland, C., & Wellmann, A. (2024). NFDI4Earth Software Architecture Documentation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534839>

⁸ ⁸ Konsortialversammlung des Vereins Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V. (2022). Stellungnahme der NFDI-Konsortien zu Basisdiensten. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6091657>

⁹ <https://www.openaire.eu/rdm-service-development-checklist>

¹⁰ <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/engage/submit-data/level-service-model>

¹¹ <https://uni-freiburg.de/cdf-en/rdm-catalogue/>

3.1. Service Catalogue

In the NFDI4Earth project, we aim to promote FAIRness and openness in future Earth System Science (ESS) research, thus we are committed to providing a portfolio overview of RDM services in the ESS community and supporting diverse stakeholders in conducting FAIR research data management. As one of the means to approach this goal, we are developing a Service Catalogue¹² that encompasses a comprehensive collection of community services. It is part of NFDI4Earth's service products and will be maintained in the Knowledge Hub.

In an early attempt during the project, we summarised an overview of institution-based RDM services and categorised them into consulting services, training services, and tools for RDM¹³. We also compiled a collection of services used for creating data management plans (DMPs)¹⁴. In response to requests from some of our pilot project partners, the Interest Group High-Performance Computing (IG HPC)¹⁵ presented an initial collection of HPC services provided by NFDI4Earth members¹⁶. During the development of the service schema, as a pilot implementation, we harvested service information from the Helmholtz DataHub¹⁷ into the Knowledge Hub using a simplified schema.

We believe that the development of metadata schema is an iteratively evolving process. As of this writing, we have substantially expanded our initial approach and developed a metadata schema (Appendix 1) for RDM services. An extensive data collection via a survey has been initiated and is in progress. Along with this procedure, we will also evaluate, adjust and improve the schema, e.g., with the service providers' feedback.

3.2. NFDI4Earth Metadata Schema for RDM Services

The presented schema is defined for a new entity class "Service" in the Knowledge Hub and encompasses 35 attribute fields, where 20 of them are required and the rest are optional. Since it is a subclass of an overarching class "Thing", "Service" inherits all attributes from "Thing", including name, description, keywords, URL, etc. The attributes specific to "Service" describes an object by its access (e.g. access type, technical and credential requirements), maintenance (e.g. business model, user support contact), data security (e.g. data processing and storage

¹² <https://nfdi4earth.de/2interoperate/architecture-synthesis>

¹³ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/livinghandbook/livinghandbook/RDM-Services/>

¹⁴ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/livinghandbook/livinghandbook/DMP-Services/>

¹⁵ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/livinghandbook/livinghandbook/IG-HPC/>

¹⁶ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/livinghandbook/livinghandbook/HPC-Services/>

¹⁷ <https://earth-data.de/>

plan, data protection and backup strategy), and some other parameters (e.g. service level, key performance indicators).

In the schema, we defined two attributes for classifying services. Attribute “serviceType” was defined to classify services based on their delivery method and user interface. To maintain consistency with existing standards and serve the purpose of (NFDI-wide) reporting, the terminology for “serviceType” is aligned with the service categories defined in de.NBI¹⁸ and NFDIcore Ontology¹⁹, which is based on the common agreement across NFDI consortia²⁰. The defined service types include: “Storage”, “Data Curation”, “Database”, “Web Application”, “Library/API”, “Workflow/Pipeline”, “Support/Consulting”, “Training”, and “Tool/Application”. For user-centric categorisation, attribute “serviceCategory” was defined to group services by the research data life cycle stage(s) they support. These categories encompass: “Data Ingestion and Curation”, “Data Storage and Management”, “Data Publication, Discovery and Access”, “Data Analysis and Visualisation”, “Interoperability and Integration”, and “User support and Training”. The definitions of individual service types and categories are available in Appendix 2.

The metadata schema for RDM service is expected to fulfil internal requirements as well as meet basic demand of interoperability with other schemas of the same type. In result, three attribute fields have been drawn from the EOSC service profile²¹: “serviceLevel”, “securityIncidentContact”, and “serviceFees”. Attribute “serviceAccessType” originates from the re3data schema²². The rest of the attribute fields were adapted from the HIFIS schema²³ or based on agreements with Base4NFDI²⁴.

An overview of the service schema is presented in Appendix 1. For attributes requiring a controlled vocabulary, i.e. “serviceType”, “serviceCategory”, “serviceLevel”, “tangibleKPI”, “serviceAccessType”, the terms and their definitions are presented in Appendix 2.

¹⁸ ¹⁸ Turewicz, M., Scholz, U., Glöckner, F. O., Dammann-Kalinowski, T., & Wittchen, M. (2022). de.NBI service category-specific KPI selection and criteria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6597826>

¹⁹ <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/>

²⁰ Amelung, L., Anthofer, V., Danabalan, R., Demandt, É., Ebert, B., Elschner, E., Espinoza, S., Eufinger, J., Fuchslöcher, S., Götz, B., Henzen, C., Hunold, J., Idda, T., Jansen, L., Krieger, U., Rodrigues, C. M., Meister, M., Miller, B., Pitroff, S., Zinke, W. (2023). White Paper: Interim Report Reference. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10101412>

²¹ <https://eosc-service-profile.readthedocs.io/en/5.0/elementsOfService.html>

²² ²² Trecker, D., Axtmann, A., Bertelmann, R., Cousijn, H., Elger, K., Ferguson, L. M., Fichtmueller, D., Jones, C., Lindenmann, I., Neidiger, C., Nguyen, T. B., Pal, J. K., Pampel, H., Petras, V., Schnepf, E., Semrau, A., Ulrich, R., Upmeyer, A., Vierkant, P., Wang, H., Weickert, G., Weisweiler, N. L., Williams, S. C., Witt, M & Wright, S. J. (2023). Metadata Schema for the Description of Research Data Repositories : version 4.0. <https://doi.org/10.48440/re3.014>

²³ <https://hifis.net/doc/>

²⁴ Schäfer-Neth, C., Grudskaja, A., Chen, T., & Giesler, A. (2025). Report on Base4NFDI service integration procedures (D2.1.1) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15235864>

4. Outlook

The presented schema will serve as the blueprint to map RDM services into the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub. Throughout the data collection process, we will continue to collect and evaluate feedback regarding the applicability of the schema and prepare for future adjustments and extensions. In addition, we aim to strengthen collaboration closely with neighboring consortia, e.g., NFDI4Biodiversity, and with Base4NFDI to foster interoperability and enhance connections to their service portfolios.

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A. Appendix 1

A.1. NFDI4Earth Service Schema

Attribute ²⁵	Description ²⁶	Data Type ²⁷	Required ²⁸	Visible to users ²⁹
name	The name of the service	String	yes	yes
description	A description about the service and its functionalities	String	yes	yes
keywords	Keywords or tags that are used to describe the service	String	yes	yes
sourceSystemURL	Link to the homepage of the service	URI	yes	yes
serviceType	A classification of services based on their delivery method and user interface	ServiceTypeEnum ³⁰	yes	no
serviceCategory	A classification of services based on the stages of the research data life cycle they support	ServiceCategoryEnum ³¹	yes	yes
linkToDocumentation	Link to documentation about the service	URI	yes	yes
imprintHostingInstitution	Essential information about the hosting institution of the service, incl. name, address, contact information, and any relevant registration and license information	URI	yes	yes
websiteHostingInstitution	The homepage of the hosting institution of the service	URI	yes	yes
idHostingInstitution	The ID of the hosting institution in the Research Organization Registry (ROR)	URI	yes	no
serviceManager	Name and Email of the person who is leading the service	Kind ³²	yes	no
serviceOwner	Name and Email of the person who is responsible for delivering the service	Kind	yes	no
firstLevelSupportContact	Name and Email of the service's first level technical support or the helpdesk at the hosting institution	Kind	yes	yes
serviceLevel	The technology readiness level of the resource	ServiceLevelEnum ³³	yes	no
businessModel	Description about the long-term financial sustainability of the service	String	yes	no
GDPRCompliant	Whether the service provider is confirmed to be compliant with GDPR	Boolean	yes	no
chargeFree	Whether the service usage is free of charge	Boolean	yes	yes

³⁰ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/ServiceTypeEnum/>

³¹ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/ServiceCategoryEnum/>

³² <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/Kind/>

³³ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/ServiceLevelEnum/>

Attribute ²⁵	Description ²⁶	Data Type ²⁷	Required ²⁸	Visible to users ²⁹
serviceAccessType	Categories for granting access to users	ServiceAccessTypeEnum ³⁴	yes	yes
servicePublicationConsent	Formal agreement from the hosting institution to publish the service metadata via NFDI4Earth services	Boolean	yes	no
contactWithPortfolioManagement	Description of how the hosting institution will communicate with the NFDI4Earth portfolio management	String	yes	no
nameAbbreviation	Abbreviation of the service name	String	no	yes
shortDescription	One-liner to be shown in the catalogue on the tile of the service	String	no	yes
logo	A picture as logo of the service	URI	no	yes
limitations	Description of maximal resources for the service, such as maximal users, maximal data volume, maximal memory / CPU etc.	String	no	no
tangibleKPI	The key performance indicators (KPI) applicable to the service; The required KPI is dependent on the service type	ServiceKPI ³⁵	no	no
userEnablement	Necessary steps of registration and authorisation for users to use the service	String	no	yes
serviceEnablement	Necessary IT components that are needed to use the service	String	no	yes
personalDataProcessingAndStorage	Description of how personal data are protected by the service provider; the description should focus on the process of where and how the personal data are processed and stored	String	no	yes
dataProtectionAndBackup	Description of data security and backup strategy, e.g. how are data protected from getting lost and stolen	String	no	yes
nonProfit	Whether the service will run on a non-profit basis	Boolean	no	yes
adFree	Whether the service will be provided without advertisements	Boolean	no	yes
securityIncidentContact	Name and Email of the person who takes care of critical security issues about the service	Kind	no	yes
serviceLocation	The geographical position where the service is based	Geometry ³⁶	no	yes
fees	Webpage containing information on the price scheme for the service	URI	no	yes
servicePrivacyPolicy	Description of how service/data privacy is maintained	URI	no	yes

³⁴ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/ServiceAccessTypeEnum/>

³⁵ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/ServiceKPI/>

³⁶ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/Geometry/>

B. Appendix 2

B.1. ServiceTypeEnum

²⁵ Name of the attribute.

²⁶ Definition of the attribute.

²⁷ Data type in which the attribute value is stored in the Knowledge Hub.

²⁸ Whether the attribute is required, "yes" for required attribute, "no" for optional attribute.

²⁹ Whether the attribute is publicly visible via OneStop4All, "yes" for visible, "no" for invisible, "uncertain" for undecided at the time of writing.

Text	Description
Storage	Provision of storage space for research data as a service to external users. Access is possible via web protocols.
Data Curation	The activity of managing and promoting the use of data from their point of creation to ensure that they are fit for contemporary purpose and available for discovery and reuse. For dynamic datasets this may mean continuous enrichment or updating to keep them fit for purpose. Higher levels of curation will also involve links with annotation and with other published material.
Database	Software that provides large amounts of structured data from repositories and archives to the user. Usually the data can be uploaded, accessed, searched and/or downloaded via a web browser.
Web Application	Software that is installed on a server and can be used by users via a web page and the internet.
Library/API	Collection of pre-implemented functions for a specific task that can be accessed via a well-defined interface.
Workflow/Pipeline	Software that combines multiple tools or applications. They may be used locally or remotely via the internet.
Support/Consulting	Service with direct user contact for topics going beyond the support for specific single services.
Training	Standalone training for self-study can be considered a technical service (usually a web application). Generally speaking, training materials often come in the form of specific measures or tutorials that are attached to a service and that are designed to improve the user's service experience. Our joint understanding of training as a stand-alone service, however, is not limited to the above and includes materials designed for education in all fields of research data management.
Tool/Application	Software that can be downloaded and executed locally on the users' hardware.

Source: de.NBI Service Category¹⁸ & NFDIcore Ontology¹⁹

B.2. ServiceCategoryEnum

Text	Description
Data Ingestion and Curation	Services that help researchers collect, organize, and curate their data according to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This includes tools for metadata management, quality assurance, and data format standardization.
Data Storage and Management	Infrastructure for secure, scalable, and sustainable storage solutions. This encompasses both short-term storage for active research and long-term archival storage for data preservation.
Data Publication, Discovery and Access	Services that provide a centralized platform or catalog for publishing data or discovering and accessing data across various repositories. This includes advanced search functionalities, data cataloging, and standardized APIs for data retrieval.
Data Analysis and Visualization	Tools and platforms that support data processing, analysis, and visualization. These services often include cloud-based computing resources, machine learning frameworks, and visualization tools tailored to Earth System Sciences.
Interoperability and Integration	Ensuring that different data formats, tools, and services can work together seamlessly. This involves developing and adhering to common standards and protocols, as well as providing middleware services that facilitate integration between disparate systems.
User Support and Training	Services designed to support users in accessing and utilizing the infrastructure effectively. This includes documentation, tutorials, workshops, and helpdesk support.

B.3. ServiceLevelEnum

Text	Description
trl1 - basic principles observed	Scientific research has led to observation and reports of basic principles which has evolved to applied research and development.
trl2 - technology concept formulated	Practical applications for the observed basic physical principles are found and reported.
trl3 - experimental proof of concept	The most critical functions of the new technology are validated by using both analytical and experimental methods.
trl4 - technology validated in lab	The concept is tested to assure that the technical elements can be integrated together and achieve the desired performance, at a component and/or breadboard level.
trl5 - technology validated in relevant environment	The components making up the concept is tested individually in realistic environment.
trl6 - technology demonstrated in relevant environment	A model or prototype of the concept, not individual components, is tested in a relevant environment.
trl7 - system prototype demonstration in operational environment	A prototype is tested in the environment in which the final product will operate.
trl8 - system complete and qualified	The technology is built to the specifications of the final product and is tested in the operational environment alongside all systems it will interact with.
trl9 - actual system proven in operational environment	At this level all technology development has been completed, and the technology is performing as intended in the real-world environment.

Source: EOSC Service Profile v.5.0³⁷

³⁷ https://eosc-service-profile.readthedocs.io/en/5.0//_vocabularies/TRL.html

B.4. ServiceAccessTypeEnum

Text	Description
Open Access	There are no access barriers.
Restricted Access	External users can overcome access barriers, e.g. by creating a user account.
Closed Access	External users cannot overcome access barriers.

Source: re3data Metadata Schema v.4.0³⁸

B.5. KPI Type

The required KPI type is related to the type of the service

Service Type	Related KPI Type (KPITypeEnum ³⁹)
Database	Total number of visits
Library/API	Total number of downloads
Workflow/Pipeline	Total number of executions
Tool/Application	Total number of downloads
Web Application	Total number of visits
Data Curation	Total number of datasets curated
Training	Total number of training activities
Storage	Total amount of provided space in GB

³⁸ https://gfzpublic.gfz-potsdam.de/rest/items/item/_5022309/_4/component/file/_5022681/content

³⁹ <https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/knowledgehub/nfdi4earth-kh-schema/KPITypeEnum/>